

Conceptual Analysis of Coastal Tourism's Carrying Capacity for Sustainable Development

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Citation :

Putri, D. O., & Taofiqurohman, A. (2025). Conceptual Analysis of Coastal Tourism's Carrying Capacity for Sustainable Development. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16753782>

Abstract

Coastal tourism plays a vital role in regional development but often brings environmental pressures if not properly managed. This paper presents a conceptual analysis of tourism carrying capacity as a framework to support sustainable coastal tourism. Drawing on the Cifuentes method, carrying capacity is assessed through three levels: physical, real, and effective. These classifications account for spatial limitations, ecological sensitivity, and management capability. Several case studies from Indonesian coastal destinations demonstrate that tourist numbers frequently exceed effective capacity during peak seasons, posing risks to environmental integrity and visitor satisfaction. The findings suggest the importance of visitor control strategies and integrated coastal area planning to maintain sustainability in coastal tourism development.

Keywords : Coastal tourism, carrying capacity, sustainable development, Cifuentes method, visitor management

Introduction

According to Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, tourism is a travel activity or part of such activity that is carried out voluntarily and is temporary in nature to enjoy tourist attractions. According to Soetomo (1994), tourism is a travel activity carried out by a person or group of people by visiting certain places for recreational purposes, personal development, or studying the uniqueness of tourist attractions visited for more than three days, which in these activities includes seeing various places both domestically and abroad (Simangunsong, 2023). A tourist attraction is an area that attracts tourists and boasts attractive natural and man-made resources, such as mountain views, coastal animals and plants, zoos, ancient historical buildings, monuments, temples, dances, and so on. M. Liga and Vanny (2015:30) divide tourism into two categories: natural tourism and socio-cultural tourism. Natural tourism includes beach tourism, ethnic tourism, nature reserve tourism, hunting travel, and agro-tourism. Meanwhile, socio-cultural tourism encompasses historical relics, monuments, museums, and cultural facilities (Pariyanti et al., 2020).

Beach tourism is a category of special interest tourism that involves activities related to the sea or marine environments. Beach tourism is a visit made by an individual or group of people with the aim of enjoying the beauty of the sea and engaging in specific activities such as swimming or simply sunbathing on the beach (Chasanah et al., 2017). Marine tourism encompasses beach tourism as well. Beach tourism, or marine tourism, is tourism

whose objects and attractions come from the potential of seascapes and coastal landscapes. Coastal tourism areas offer a variety of tourism activities, encompassing both the seascape and the coastal landscape (Nuraini, 2017).

Traveler

According to Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, a tourist is a person who travels. According to Suwanto (2004), a tourist is a person or group of people who travel for a period of more than 24 hours in the area or country visited. *The International Union of Official Travel Organizations* defines tourism broadly, stating that a visitor is any person who arrives in a country or other place of residence for any purpose except for the purpose of working for wages (Simangunsong, 2023). According to Musanef (1995) in Damara et al. (2014), tourists can be categorized into two categories, namely:

1. International tourists are defined as those who travel for at least 24 hours and up to 3 months to a country other than their own, or who visit a country without the intention of settling or working permanently.
2. Domestic tourists, namely tourists who travel to other places where the tourists reside, or tourists who visit a place that is still within the scope of the country where the tourists reside.
3. Sustainable Tourism

Indonesia implements integrated tourism development through cross-sectoral coordination, striving for maximum success. To achieve this success, effective management and development require collaboration among local communities, businesses, the central government, and regional governments, as stipulated in Article 11 of Law No. 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism. This success aims to increase Regional Original Income (PAD) (Fadisa et al., 2022).

Development activities and the utilization of natural resources are physical events that occur in the environment and have many impacts, such as changing environmental conditions. Therefore, sustainable tourism development must prioritize environmental sustainability. *Sustainable tourism is a rapidly growing sector that includes increases in accommodation capacity, local population, and environmental considerations; this type of tourism development aims to avoid negative impacts and promote harmony with the environment, thereby maximizing positive effects and minimizing negative ones (Widiati & Permatasari, 2022).*

Tourism Carrying Capacity

According to UNWTO (1984), tourism carrying capacity *is* the maximum number of tourists who can visit a tourist destination at the same time without causing negative impacts on the physical, economic, and socio-cultural environment and an unacceptable decline in quality for tourist satisfaction (Salusu et al., 2023).

According to the Department of Culture and Tourism (2009), aspects of tourism carrying capacity that need to be considered are the number of tourists per year, the length of tourist visits, how often ecologically vulnerable locations can be visited, etc. The quality of visitor satisfaction and comfort in enjoying tourism activities closely correlates with this tourism carrying capacity. If the number of tourists exceeds the tourism carrying capacity, it can reduce both tourist comfort and satisfaction due to overcrowding (Lucyanti et al., 2013).

Cifuentes Analysis Method

Cifuentes (1992) and Cifuentes et al. (1999) developed the method to estimate the physical ecological factors related to carrying capacity. By taking into account the physical, biological, and management conditions of an area, this method can estimate the maximum number of tourists it can support. In estimating the maximum number of tourists, there are three types of carrying capacities: physical carrying capacity, real *carrying capacity*, and *effective carrying capacity* (Huamantincó Cisneros et al., 2016).

Carrying capacity is the maximum number of tourists who can physically enter an area within a certain time. Physical factors and security risks can limit the available area. Real carrying capacity is the number of tourists allowed to enter an area within a *certain* time. *This number is determined by applying a correction factor (CF) that considers the characteristics of the area to the physical carrying capacity.* Effective carrying capacity is the maximum number of tourists that can be accommodated in an area while still considering the management capacity factor (MC). Management capacity is the ability of the tourism management organization to meet and support the needs of tourists when visiting the tourist area.

In a study (Sofiyani et al., 2019) that analyzed the physical, real, and effective carrying capacity of the ecotourism area on Pisang Island in 2019, the results indicated that the physical carrying capacity on Pisang Island was 175,000 people/day, with the real and effective carrying capacities at 27,887 people/day and 744 people/day, respectively. From the results of the carrying capacity and data on the number of tourists visiting Pisang Island on weekdays, it is still below the carrying capacity value, but the number of tourists during holidays has exceeded the effective carrying capacity, so it is necessary to implement tourist restrictions during holidays so that tourist attractions and the quality of visits are maintained.

In a study (Millah & Fadlina, 2023) that analyzed the carrying capacity *in* supporting the development of the Batukaras Beach tourism destination in Pangandaran Regency, the physical carrying capacity value was 4,707 people/day, while the real carrying capacity was 1,315 people/day and the effective carrying capacity was 1,048 people/day. The number of tourists during the study on weekdays was 741 people/day, meaning the number of tourists visiting Batukaras Beach was still below the effective carrying capacity threshold. Meanwhile, on holidays, the number of tourists reached 2,462 people/day, exceeding the carrying capacity limit and potentially impacting the environment.

In a study (Maryono et al., 2019) on tourism carrying capacity for coastal management development in Tanjung Bira, the physical carrying capacity was 2,257 people/day, the real carrying capacity was 202 people/day, and the effective carrying capacity was 117 people/day. Based on these results, it is hoped that implementing a tourist limit of 117–202 people per day, within the effective and real carrying capacity, will be an effort to preserve the ecosystem in the coastal area and its surroundings. Another solution to reducing the number of tourists is expanding the coastal area. For example, combining Tanjung Bira Beach with Bira Beach can increase the tourist area and the number of visitors per day.

Insani et al., 2020 conducted a study to estimate the carrying capacity for coastal tourism management at Ungapan Beach. From the results of the study, it was found that the physical carrying capacity was 12,960 people/day, for the real carrying capacity of 1,992 people/day and the effective carrying capacity of 1,533 people/day. The results of the physical carrying capacity, real carrying capacity, and effective carrying capacity were then classified based on the type and recommendations for tourism carrying capacity. The

result is that Ungapan Beach is included in the classification of large carrying capacity and is recommended for further development because, in the results of the carrying capacity calculation, the physical carrying capacity at Ungapan Beach is greater than the real carrying capacity.

Summary

This document explores the concept of carrying capacity in coastal tourism as part of sustainable development. It emphasizes the importance of managing tourism to avoid environmental damage and ensure a positive visitor experience. Using the Cifuentes method, carrying capacity is assessed in three levels: physical, real, and effective. Case studies from several beaches reveal that visitor numbers often exceed the effective capacity during holidays, highlighting the need for visitor limits or expanded tourism areas to maintain environmental quality and sustainability.

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